

Green Human Resource Management and Organizational Citizenship

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Abstract:

In today's competitive business landscape, sustainability is paramount, particularly within the tourism sector where organizations must balance financial performance with environmental stewardship. This study investigates the implementation of Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) and Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment (OCBE) among employees of a Filipino hotel chain in Western Visayas. Utilizing an explanatory sequential mixed methods design, the quantitative phase surveyed 41 employees to assess the extent of GHRM and OCBE practices, while the qualitative phase conducted in-depth interviews with six employees to explore their experiences and perceptions. Results indicate a very high level of GHRM implementation, especially in green human capital, green training and development, environmental performance, and green structural capital. Conversely, pro-environmental behavior was rated lower, suggesting areas for improvement. Older employees exhibited significantly higher engagement in certain GHRM practices, although no significant differences were observed based on sex or length of stay. A positive correlation ($r = 0.537$, $p < 0.001$) was found between GHRM practices and OCBE, highlighting the interdependent relationship between structured HR initiatives and voluntary environmental behaviors. Qualitative findings corroborate the quantitative data, revealing a culture of environmental stewardship supported by empathetic leadership and comprehensive employee benefits. The study concludes that robust GHRM practices in the said institution foster OCBE, enhancing its organizational sustainability and reputation. Recommendations include enhancing pro-environmental initiatives, strengthening training programs, formalizing environmental policies, and promoting inclusive leadership to further advance sustainability goals within the hospitality industry.

Keywords: Green Human Resource Management, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Environmental Sustainability, Hospitality Industry, Employee Engagement, Pro-environmental Behavior, Mixed Methods, Philippine Hotel Chain

Introduction

In today's hypercompetitive business environment, organizations face significant challenges in sustaining financial performance, cost-effectiveness, and growth. This is particularly evident in the tourism sector, where businesses must navigate intense competition while striving to maintain sustainable operations. To achieve sustainable financial performance, it is imperative for tourism businesses to integrate environmentalism and Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) practices into their organizational policies. Abdeen and Ahmed (2019) emphasize that fostering green employees—those who understand, appreciate, practice green initiatives, and uphold green objectives—is crucial for the long-term viability of these businesses.

Hotels, as a critical segment of the tourism industry, are increasingly adopting various sustainability practices to achieve beneficial outcomes. Salama et al. (2022) highlight that hotels aim to address community needs by cultivating a culture of environmental responsibility. This is accomplished through the implementation of functions within an environmental management system, which underscores the importance of integrating sustainability into core business operations. Concurrently, recent studies on company performance management have underscored the significance of organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) and GHRM practices in enhancing organizational productivity and effectiveness. Kang et al. (2020) argue that service-oriented businesses must inspire employees to adopt an energetic and voluntary attitude towards tasks to boost overall organizational performance.

GHRM plays a pivotal role in embedding environmental management within human resource practices, thereby reducing pollution and promoting sustainable operational processes (Pham et al., 2020; Renwick et al., 2012). This approach encompasses various HR activities, including recruitment, performance management, training and development, employment relations, compensation, and exit strategies, all aligned with environmental management philosophies (Saeed et al., 2019). Benevene and Buonomo (2020) posit that GHRM practices are predictive of environmental performance, suggesting that organizational greening initiatives positively influence overall performance metrics. The critical role of employees in achieving organizational greening through pro-environmental behaviors is widely acknowledged (Lülfes & Rüdiger, 2013; Opatha & Arulraja, 2014; Saeed et al., 2019).

Green hiring, defined as the recruitment of individuals possessing the necessary knowledge, skills, attitudes, and behaviors aligned with green management (Jeganathan et al., 2019; Farghaly et al., 2021), is essential for minimizing an organization's negative environmental impact and enhancing sustainable performance (Martins et al., 2021). Complementing this, green training—which includes on-the-job training and supplementary education aimed at integrating environmental management goals—has been identified as a key factor in overcoming barriers to

environmental protection and fostering acceptance of green practices in the workplace (Yafi et al., 2021; Nisar et al., 2021).

Despite the growing recognition of green human resource management (GHRM)'s importance, recent research within the hospitality and tourism literature has predominantly focused on Western contexts, with limited studies addressing the Philippine setting. This research gap is particularly evident in the Philippine hotel industry, where, although hotels have written environmental policies for employees to follow, these policies are not widely known among staff. Instead, employees often engage in environmental conservation acts voluntarily. Motivated by this gap, the current study seeks to develop an enhanced policy program based on findings related to GHRM and Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment (OCBE) within a Filipino hotel chain brand in Western Visayas. By focusing on the unique context of the Philippines, this research aims to provide tailored strategies that bolster the effectiveness of environmental policies and promote sustainable practices within the local hospitality sector.

This study primarily aims to assess the extent of Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) implementation and Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment (OCBE) among employees of a Filipino hotel chain. It seeks to explore employee experiences through qualitative interviews and examine the differences in the implementation of GHRM and OCBE practices based on demographic variables such as age, sex, and length of stay within the company. Additionally, the research intends to investigate the potential correlations between GHRM practices and OCBE, thereby contributing to the development of effective strategies for enhancing business sustainability in the hospitality sector. To achieve these objectives, the study posits several hypotheses. Firstly, it hypothesizes that there is no significant difference in the level of implementation of GHRM across various aspects—namely green hiring, green training and development, green discipline management, green human capital, green structural capital, pro-environmental behavior, and environmental performance—when employees are grouped by age, sex, and length of stay. Secondly, the study suggests that there is no significant difference in the extent of OCBE, specifically in eco-initiatives, eco-civic engagement, and eco-helping, among employees categorized by the same demographic variables. Lastly, it hypothesizes that there is no significant relationship between the extent of GHRM implementation and the level of OCBE exhibited by employees of the Filipino hotel brand. By addressing these hypotheses, the study seeks to fill existing research gaps within the Philippine context and provide actionable insights to enhance the effectiveness of environmental policies and sustainable practices in the local hospitality industry.

Review of Related Literature

Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) integrates environmental management into human resource practices, emphasizing HR's role in promoting sustainable operational processes and reducing pollution (Pham et al., 2020; Renwick et al., 2012). GHRM encompasses various HR activities, including green recruitment and selection, green training and development, green performance management, green compensation and rewards, and green exit strategies, all aimed at fostering an environmentally conscious workforce (Saeed et al., 2019). According to Benevene and Buonomo (2020), GHRM practices are significant predictors of an organization's environmental performance, as they encourage employees to engage in environmentally responsible behaviors that benefit individuals, society, and the natural environment.

GHRM practices have been shown to enhance organizational performance by promoting pro-environmental behaviors among employees. Lülfs and Rüdiger (2013) and Opatha and Arulraja (2014) assert that employees play a vital role in implementing green initiatives, which are essential for achieving organizational sustainability. Saeed et al. (2019) further highlight that GHRM practices not only support environmental objectives but also contribute to the overall effectiveness and productivity of the organization.

Green hiring involves selecting employees based on their environmental awareness, skills, and behaviors that align with the organization's green management objectives (Jeganathan et al., 2019; Farghaly et al., 2021). Martins et al. (2021) emphasize that green hiring is crucial for minimizing an organization's negative environmental impact and achieving sustainable performance. By prioritizing candidates with a strong understanding of environmental issues and a commitment to sustainability, organizations can enhance their environmental management strategies and gain a competitive edge (Ovais & Shaiq, 2024; Shah, 2019). Additionally, green hiring fosters eco-values among employees, thereby promoting a culture of environmental responsibility within the organization (Alshehri et al., 2024).

Green Training and Development (GTD) aims to equip employees with the knowledge and skills necessary to implement sustainable practices, such as energy conservation and waste reduction (Alqudah & Yusof, 2024). Ahmad et al. (2023) assert that green training directly influences a hotel's environmental performance by raising employee awareness and competence in sustainability practices. Furthermore, GTD serves as a pro-social strategy that enhances employee performance and promotes organizational sustainability through continuous learning and adaptation (Khattak et al., 2023; Gul et al., 2023). Jiang et al. (2022) note that green training helps employees become more agile in adopting energy-efficient practices and reducing workplace waste, thereby contributing to the organization's sustainability goals.

Green Discipline Management involves enforcing environmental policies through guidelines, monitoring compliance, and ensuring adherence to green practices (Darvazeh et al., 2023). Ridwan (2023) highlights that systematic disciplinary procedures are essential for maintaining organizational discipline and fostering employee growth. By implementing green discipline management, organizations can mitigate harmful environmental effects and enhance their environmental management strategies (Liu, 2023; Ali et al., 2023). This approach not only supports ecological preservation but also strengthens the organization's competitive advantage through eco-friendly innovations and strategies (Ali Nisar et al., 2021).

Green Human Capital refers to the environmentally conscious skills, knowledge, and competencies that employees possess, which support and drive sustainable practices within an organization (Bag & Gupta, 2019; Chiappetta Jabbour et al., 2019; Agyabeng-Mensah & Tang, 2021). Yusoff et al. (2019) describe green human capital as a core resource for achieving sustainable competitive advantage, as it is difficult to imitate and thus provides a unique value proposition for organizations. In the hospitality industry, green human capital is essential for implementing sustainability initiatives such as water and energy conservation and waste management (Dewi et al., 2023). Slavković et al. (2023) argue that effective utilization of green human capital is crucial for creating differentiated services and enhancing organizational performance.

Green Structural Capital encompasses the organizational capacity, knowledge management systems, management viewpoints, organizational culture, business image, and intellectual property related to environmental protection and green improvements (Shan Chen, 2008; Widayastuti et al., 2021). Zhang et al. (2020) assert that green structural capital significantly impacts an organization's sustainability performance by supporting green innovation and enhancing the organization's reputation. Karimi et al. (2023) emphasize that robust green structural capital enables the effective use of human capital and fosters innovation, thereby contributing to sustainable performance and competitive positioning. Martínez-Falcó et al. (2023) highlight that green structural capital integrates human, structural, and relational knowledge, which is essential for achieving sustainable organizational performance.

Pro-environmental behavior involves actions undertaken by employees to minimize their negative impact on the environment, such as reducing resource consumption, conserving energy, and minimizing waste production (Hong & Xinyu, 2022). Sampene et al. (2024) indicate that pro-environmental behavior is crucial for improving an organization's environmental performance and addressing ecological challenges. In the tourism sector, where environmental pressures are significant, promoting pro-environmental behaviors among employees and stakeholders is essential for mitigating negative impacts on destination resources (Težak Damijanić et al., 2023; Holmes et al., 2021). Effective training, assessment, and incentive systems can further encourage employees to engage in pro-environmental activities (Ullah et al., 2021).

Environmental performance refers to the extent to which an organization's practices align with societal expectations for environmental stewardship, going beyond basic regulatory compliance to enhance the organization's image, customer satisfaction, and loyalty (Muhammad et al., 2020; Kularatne et al., 2019). Asadi et al. (2020) found that environmental regulations, eco-innovation strategies, and a green organizational culture positively influence a business's economic performance. Effective GHRM practices are instrumental in improving environmental performance by aligning HR activities with sustainability objectives, thereby enhancing the overall performance of the organization (Singh et al., 2020; Abdeen & Ahmed, 2019).

Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment (OCBE) encompasses voluntary and discretionary employee actions that contribute to environmental sustainability but are not formally recognized by existing reward systems or environmental management policies (Sihombing & Iqbal, 2024). OCBE includes eco-initiatives, eco-civic engagement, and eco-helping behaviors, which collectively enhance an organization's environmental performance and corporate image (Elshaer et al., 2022; Abdou et al., 2023). Eco-initiatives involve self-driven practices that promote environmental preservation, while eco-civic engagement refers to community involvement activities aimed at enhancing environmental welfare (Ye & Li, 2024). Eco-helping denotes employee-driven efforts to support colleagues in adopting environmentally conscious behaviors (Uddin, 2019; Nazneen et al., 2024). The integration of OCBE into organizational practices fosters a culture of environmental stewardship and can lead to improved sustainability outcomes (Vakira et al., 2023).

The Ability Motivation Opportunity (AMO) Theory provides a theoretical framework for understanding how organizational practices influence employee behavior. According to Appelbaum, Bailey, et al. (2000), employee performance can be enhanced when their abilities, motivations, and opportunities are adequately developed. Fawehinmi et al. (2023) apply this theory to green practices, suggesting that GHRM practices enhance employees' abilities through green recruitment and training, boost motivation through performance management and rewards for eco-friendly competencies, and provide opportunities for participation in sustainability activities (Acquah et al., 2020; Aggarwal & Agarwala, 2023). This theoretical perspective underscores the importance of comprehensive GHRM practices in fostering pro-environmental behaviors and achieving sustainability goals.

Laudato Si' is an encyclical letter by Pope Francis that emphasizes the importance of caring for our common home, the Earth, and promoting ecological virtues among humanity (Francis, 2019; Kureethadam, 2016). The Ecological Society of America (ESA) describes Laudato Si' as a call for responsible stewardship informed by scientific understanding of environmental challenges, their impacts on humanity, and the necessity for intergenerational equity (Raven, 2016). This global perspective on environmental responsibility aligns with organizational efforts to implement OCBE, as it encourages employees to adopt stewardship values and engage in behaviors that support environmental sustainability (Sihombing & Iqbal, 2024).

The integration of Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) and Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment (OCBE) is essential for enhancing environmental performance and achieving sustainable business practices in the hospitality industry. This review underscores the critical role of GHRM practices in fostering a green workforce and promoting pro-environmental behaviors among employees. Additionally, OCBE serves as a vital component in cultivating a culture of environmental stewardship, further contributing to organizational sustainability. The theoretical framework provided by the Ability Motivation Opportunity (AMO) Theory supports the implementation of comprehensive GHRM practices to drive sustainable outcomes. Furthermore, the principles outlined in Laudato Si' reinforce the importance of responsible environmental stewardship within organizational contexts. Collectively, these insights provide a robust foundation for developing effective policies and strategies aimed at enhancing business sustainability in the hospitality sector.

Methodology:

This study employed an explanatory sequential mixed methods design to investigate the implementation of Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) and Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment (OCBE) among employees of a Filipino hotel chain in Western Visayas. The design facilitated the collection and analysis of quantitative data followed by qualitative data, thereby enhancing the understanding of the quantitative findings through in-depth qualitative insights (Hirose & Creswell, 2023).

Quantitative Phase

The quantitative phase targeted organic employees of a Filipino hotel brand operating in Bacolod City and Iloilo City, Western Visayas. A total of 41 employees participated in the survey, representing both managerial and rank-and-file positions within the organization. Stratified proportionate allocation sampling was employed to ensure the sample accurately reflected the demographic composition of the employee population in terms of age, sex, and length of stay with the company.

Data collection for the quantitative phase was conducted using an adapted and modified questionnaire structured into three sections. The first section collected demographic information, including age, sex, and length of experience with the company. The second section encompassed the dimensions of GHRM, comprising 39 questions, while the third section focused on the dimensions of OCBE, consisting of ten questions. Responses were measured on a 4-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (lowest extent) to 4 (highest extent).

The questionnaire's validity was established using Lawshe's content validity ratio (Lawshe, 1975). Twelve subject matter experts reviewed the instrument, and the content validity index was calculated to be 0.935, surpassing the critical value of 0.6, thereby confirming the instrument's validity. To assess reliability, Cronbach's Alpha was utilized following a pilot test with 30 respondents. The GHRM section achieved an alpha coefficient of 0.94, and the OCBE section achieved 0.842, indicating high internal consistency and reliability of the instrument.

Data collection commenced with obtaining permission through formal letters addressed to the general managers of the target hotel properties. Upon approval, virtual meetings were conducted with the hotel's director of human resources and relevant department heads to explain the study's purpose, significance, and ethical considerations. The survey was then administered online to ensure accessibility and convenience for the employees. To maintain data security, all survey responses were stored on a password-protected computer. Following the completion of the survey, the quantitative data were analyzed to inform the subsequent qualitative phase of the study.

Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Mean scores and standard deviations were calculated to address the extent of GHRM and OCBE implementation. To determine significant differences in GHRM and OCBE practices based on demographic variables (age, sex, and length of stay), independent samples t-tests and Mann-Whitney U tests were employed. Pearson's correlation coefficient was utilized to examine the relationship between GHRM practices and OCBE. The interpretation of mean scores followed a predefined range: 3.26-4.00 indicated a very high extent, 2.51-3.25 a high extent, 1.76-2.50 a low extent, and 1.00-1.75 a very low extent of implementation.

Qualitative Phase

The qualitative phase adopted a narrative inquiry approach, which focuses on collecting and analyzing individuals' stories to gain deeper insights into their experiences and perceptions (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). This approach was selected to complement the quantitative findings by providing contextual and nuanced understanding of employee experiences with GHRM and OCBE practices.

Six employees from two properties of the Filipino hotel chain in Western Visayas served as primary data sources for the qualitative phase. Participants included both managerial and rank-and-file employees who met the inclusion criteria: being an organic employee of the hotel brand, having a minimum of one year of tenure, and holding either a managerial or rank-and-file position.

After the quantitative data analysis, six participants were purposively selected for semi-structured, audio-recorded interviews lasting between 60 to 90 minutes. The selection aimed to ensure a diverse representation of experiences and perspectives. The interviews were conducted virtually to accommodate participants' schedules and were subsequently transcribed for analysis. All audio recordings were securely stored in a password-protected drive and were scheduled for complete disposal upon the study's conclusion.

Data analysis for the qualitative phase followed Lichman's (2013) 3Cs method, which involves coding, categorizing, and conceptualizing. Initially, selective coding was performed by meticulously reading and re-reading the interview transcripts to identify significant codes, while eliminating redundant ones (Hosami, 2019). In the categorizing stage, these codes were organized into themes aligned with the study's objectives through an iterative process of revisiting and modifying categories as necessary. Finally, conceptualizing involved refining the categories to develop coherent themes that were richly supported by participants' statements, ensuring that the final themes accurately reflected the data.

To ensure the trustworthiness of the qualitative data, several strategies were employed. Credibility was achieved through member checking and triangulation by sources, involving feedback from participants and data collected from both managerial and rank-and-file employees (Lincoln & Guba, 1985; Nowell et al., 2017). Transferability was addressed through purposeful sampling and detailed descriptions of research activities, allowing readers to assess the applicability of findings to other contexts (Creswell & Clark, 2017). Dependability was ensured by documenting all research activities and employing the code-recode strategy to verify data consistency (Broussard, 2023). Confirmability was established through an audit trail, which provided a transparent record of the research process and verified that findings were data-driven (Lincoln & Guba, 1985; Korstjens & Moser, 2018).

The methodological framework of this study, encompassing both quantitative and qualitative phases, was meticulously designed to explore and understand the implementation of GHRM and OCBE within a Filipino hotel chain in Western Visayas. The quantitative phase provided a broad overview of the extent of these practices, while the qualitative phase offered in-depth insights into employee experiences and perceptions. Together, these methods ensured a comprehensive analysis, thereby contributing valuable knowledge to the field of sustainable human resource management in the hospitality industry.

Results

The quantitative phase of the study involved 41 organic employees from a Filipino hotel brand located in Bacolod City and Iloilo City, Western Visayas. The analysis focused on assessing the extent of implementation of Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) practices and Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment (OCBE) among these employees.

Extent of Implementation of GHRM Practices

Overall, the implementation of GHRM practices was rated at a very high extent, with a mean score of 3.26 (SD = 0.34). Among the seven dimensions of GHRM, green human capital (mean = 3.55, SD = 0.45), green training and development (mean = 3.50, SD = 0.46), environmental performance (mean = 3.48, SD = 0.45), and green structural capital (mean = 3.43, SD = 0.50) were rated very high. Green discipline management received a high rating with a mean of 3.23 (SD = 0.54), while pro-environmental behavior was notably lower, with a mean score of 2.47 (SD = 0.42).

When grouped by age, older employees reported significantly higher implementation of green training and development (mean = 3.67, SD = 0.42) compared to younger employees (mean = 3.39, SD = 0.45), $p = 0.049$. Additionally, green human capital (mean = 3.78, SD = 0.34 vs. mean = 3.41, SD = 0.46, $p = 0.008$) and green structural capital (mean = 3.62, SD = 0.42 vs. mean = 3.30, SD = 0.52, $p = 0.046$) were significantly more implemented among older employees. No significant differences were observed in green hiring, green discipline management, pro-environmental behavior, or environmental performance based on age.

Sex-based analysis revealed that female employees rated green human capital highest (mean = 3.65, SD = 0.46), followed by green structural capital (mean = 3.50, SD = 0.55) and environmental performance (mean = 3.61, SD = 0.40). However, no significant differences were found between male and female employees across any of the GHRM dimensions ($p > 0.05$).

Regarding length of stay, employees with longer tenure reported a higher extent of green training and development (mean = 3.58, SD = 0.42) compared to those with shorter tenure (mean = 3.40, SD = 0.50), $p = 0.046$. No significant differences were found in other GHRM dimensions based on length of stay ($p > 0.05$).

Extent of Implementation of OCBE Practices

OCBE practices were collectively implemented at a very high extent, with an overall mean score of 3.50 (SD = 0.36). Among the three dimensions of OCBE, eco-helping was rated highest (mean = 3.52, SD = 0.44), followed by eco-initiatives (mean = 3.50, SD = 0.44) and eco-civic engagement (mean = 3.49, SD = 0.43).

When grouped by age, older employees scored significantly higher in eco-initiatives (mean = 3.69, SD = 0.41) compared to younger employees (mean = 3.37, SD = 0.41), $p = 0.028$. No significant differences were found in eco-civic engagement or eco-helping based on age. Sex-based analysis revealed no significant differences in the extent of OCBE practices between female and male employees ($p > 0.05$), although female employees slightly outperformed males in eco-initiatives (mean = 3.54, SD = 0.42 vs. mean = 3.45, SD = 0.46). Length of stay did not significantly affect the extent of OCBE practices across any dimensions ($p > 0.05$), indicating consistent engagement in environmental stewardship regardless of tenure.

A Pearson correlation analysis demonstrated a significant positive relationship between the extent of GHRM implementation and OCBE ($r = 0.537$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting that higher levels of GHRM practices are associated with greater engagement in OCBE among employees.

Qualitative Findings

The qualitative data further elucidated these findings, revealing five key themes: Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), Pro-Environmental Behavior, Environmental Performance, Green Human Capital, and Employee Benefits.

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB): OCB was characterized by employees' voluntary participation in eco-initiatives, eco-civic engagement, and eco-helping. Employees described various activities such as plastic collection, gardening, clean-up drives, and tree planting. For example, Charlestone noted, "Voluntary if we want to collect or not, because we in the management are required at least to show that staff that we are doing what management asks of us. We see that there are people who are willing to help." Caroline emphasized the camaraderie fostered through participation in environmental activities, stating, "Joining the activities also promotes camaraderie among me and my colleagues... it's really enjoyable."

Pro-Environmental Behavior: Rooted in environmental consciousness, pro-environmental behavior included practices like water conservation, waste segregation, and participation in environmental preservation projects. Betina shared the initiation of an urban garden project, explaining its role in sustainability and cost reduction: "We will be able to save a lot of food cost because we're spending so much to buy vegetables... it will really cost you less." Charlestone discussed systematic approaches to managing waste within the hotel, particularly for plastics and papers.

Environmental Performance: Environmental performance was evidenced by sustainable practices such as urban gardening, refillable water bottles, and plastic recycling. Betina highlighted the financial benefits of the urban garden, while Charlestone added that transitioning to refillable bottles reduced costs significantly: "We've saved so much with the glass bottles compared to plastics."

Green Human Capital: Encompassing employees' environmental understanding, capabilities, and commitments, green human capital was highlighted through positive experiences with management's support and the company's culture of empathy and teamwork. Betina appreciated the fair treatment and emphasis on empathy, while Charlestone and Caroline highlighted the supportive and family-oriented management practices that fostered a harmonious work environment. Irene emphasized the training provided on chemical usage and waste segregation, demonstrating the company's commitment to building green human capital.

Employee Benefits: Employee benefits emerged as crucial for attracting and retaining talent. Interviewees praised the company's medical benefits, training opportunities, and supportive policies. Charlestone shared a personal experience of the company supporting him during a family health crisis, stating, "HR took care of everything... that's why I don't want to leave here." Caroline and Irene also emphasized the company's commitment to employee well-being and career growth through comprehensive benefits and training programs.

Discussion

The study's findings underscore a robust implementation of Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) practices within the Filipino hotel chain in Western Visayas, particularly excelling in green human capital, green training and development, environmental performance, and green structural capital. These dimensions received very high mean scores, suggesting that the organization effectively integrates environmental sustainability into its HRM practices. This is consistent with Pham et al. (2019), who emphasized the importance of green training in enhancing employees' discretionary efforts towards sustainability. Furthermore, the high ratings in green structural capital and environmental performance corroborate the assertions of Saeed et al. (2019) that GHRM practices significantly contribute to overall organizational effectiveness and sustainability.

However, the lower rating in the pro-environmental behavior dimension indicates a potential area for improvement. This finding suggests that while the organization has established strong GHRM frameworks, there may be gaps in fostering proactive environmental behaviors among employees. This aligns with Lülfs and Rüdiger (2013) and Opatha and Arulraja (2014), who noted the critical role of employees in implementing green initiatives. The qualitative data further supports this by illustrating that while employees are engaged in various environmental initiatives, these actions are often voluntary and may benefit from more structured incentives and recognition systems. This underscores the need for management to develop targeted programs that reinforce and encourage such behaviors, potentially through enhanced training, incentives, and recognition mechanisms.

Age-based analyses revealed that older employees reported significantly higher levels of green training and development, green human capital, and green structural capital. This suggests that more experienced employees may be better integrated into the organization's sustainability initiatives, possibly due to longer exposure to GHRM practices. This finding is supported by Jerónimo et al. (2020), who highlighted that older employees tend to exhibit stronger environmental commitments. Conversely, the lack of significant differences in pro-environmental behavior across age groups indicates that interventions to boost such behaviors should be uniformly applied, regardless of age.

The absence of significant differences in GHRM implementation across sexes suggests that the organization's policies are effectively inclusive, ensuring that both male and female employees equally benefit from and participate in GHRM practices. This supports the notion of gender-neutral HRM practices as advocated by Gülsoy and Ustabaş (2019) and Alcalde-Rubio et al. (2020), promoting an equitable work environment conducive to sustainability.

Length of stay analysis indicated that employees with longer tenure experienced higher levels of green training and development. This finding aligns with the literature that suggests longer-tenured employees are more likely to receive comprehensive training and support (Rahman & Raju, 2020). However, the lack of significant differences in other GHRM dimensions based on tenure suggests that the organization maintains consistent GHRM practices across all employees, irrespective of their length of service.

The significant positive correlation between GHRM and OCBE practices underscores the interdependent relationship between structured HRM initiatives and voluntary environmental behaviors. This relationship highlights the importance of integrating GHRM practices to foster a culture of sustainability, as supported by Hameed et al. (2020) and Muisyo et al. (2022). Effective GHRM practices not only provide the necessary training and resources but also create an organizational environment that encourages employees to engage in pro-environmental behaviors willingly.

The qualitative themes provide deeper insights into the mechanisms through which GHRM practices influence OCBE. Organizational Citizenship Behavior, characterized by voluntary environmental initiatives and civic engagement, reflects a strong organizational culture that values and supports environmental sustainability. The interviews indicate that management's support and the company's values of empathy and teamwork play a critical role in fostering such behaviors, aligning with Youn and Kim (2022) and Astry et al. (2023).

Environmental performance, as evidenced by sustainable practices like urban gardening and refillable water bottles, demonstrates the hotel's commitment to reducing its ecological footprint. These initiatives not only enhance operational efficiency and cost savings but also contribute to the hotel's reputation as a sustainable establishment, supporting findings by Ali Nisar et al. (2021).

Green human capital, underscored by positive employee experiences and comprehensive training programs, indicates the hotel's success in embedding environmental values within its workforce. The supportive and family-oriented management practices contribute to a harmonious and motivated workforce, essential for the effective implementation of GHRM practices.

Employee benefits, particularly medical benefits and training opportunities, emerged as key factors in enhancing employee commitment and engagement. The qualitative data illustrated that comprehensive benefits and supportive

policies not only aid in employee retention but also foster a sense of loyalty and belonging, which are critical for sustaining GHRM and OCBE practices. Charlestone’s account of the company supporting him during a family health crisis exemplifies how employee benefits can significantly impact employee loyalty and organizational commitment.

Joint Display of Results

Highlighted Dimensions	Quantitative Result	Qualitative Result	Meta Inference
Green Human Resource Management			
Green Training and Development Pro-environmental behavior	GHRM’s level of implementation of a Filipino hotel chain brand was rated as very high extent with the mean score of 3.26 and a standard deviation of 0.34. This result implies that the hotel implements green human resource management practices in a desirable manner. Meanwhile, among the dimensions, green training and development is presumed to be effectively carried out by the management to their employees, while pro – environmental behavior may need to be reinforced to be further evident.	Among the dimensions of GHRM, the environmental performance dimension was the most richly described and mentioned by the conversation partners.	The researcher infers that the employees of the hotel are greatly engaged in activities that are focused on environmental conservation efforts which are corroborative for both quantitative and qualitative results. This engagement may be helpful in strengthening the hotel’s external reputation as an environmentally friendly institution thereby creating a positive business reputation to both its external and internal stakeholders.

Highlighted Dimensions	Quantitative Result	Qualitative Result	Meta Inference
Organizational Citizenship Behavior			
Eco – Helping Eco- Initiatives	When taken collectively, the overall mean score of extent of OCBE was 3.50 and a standard deviation of 0.36 is verbally interpreted as a very high extent. This implies that the employee’s level of volunteerism towards environmental protection is evident regardless of not having a formal reward system for their personal voluntary environmental protection efforts.	Based on the conducted audio recorded interview with 6 conversation partners, the premise of volunteerism on environmental conservation activities were mentioned across all who were interviewed. It was further mentioned by the conversation partners that involving and participating in activities such as cleanup drive, tree planting,	The employees were able to embody environmental stewardship for the environment; this may imply that the management’s effort of cascading the company’s corporate values of “Malasakit” or care for their colleagues, as well for the environment was effectively cascaded. Thus, the result of such effective cascading has already turned into their day-to-day culture in the workplace according to the qualitative data that were collected. The researcher infers therefore that this may positively impact the reputation of the hotel as an establishment where people genuinely care for the

		<p>bloodletting, etc. were purely voluntary and these involvements or participation need not to be formally recognized as they do these acts at their own freewill.</p>	<p>environment. Hence, creating a positive reputation in introducing the hotel brand in the market. For the internal operations, having a high OCBE implementation may help lower costs, save on existing resources, and sustain limited resources for the business, thru promoting a circular economy.</p>
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The integration of both quantitative and qualitative data provides a comprehensive understanding of how GHRM practices influence OCBE within the hotel. While the quantitative data highlights the overall high implementation of GHRM practices and their positive correlation with OCBE, the qualitative data enriches these findings by offering detailed insights into employee experiences and perceptions. This mixed-methods approach validates the quantitative results and adds depth to the understanding of the underlying mechanisms at play.

Conclusion:

The comprehensive analysis of both quantitative and qualitative data reveals that the Filipino hotel brand in Western Visayas exhibits a high level of implementation of Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) practices. Specifically, dimensions such as green human capital, green training and development, environmental performance, and green structural capital were rated very high, indicating a strong integration of environmental sustainability into the organization's HRM framework. These findings corroborate existing literature, which posits that effective GHRM practices enhance organizational sustainability and employee engagement (Pham et al., 2019; Saeed et al., 2019).

Furthermore, the study found that employees demonstrated a high degree of Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment (OCBE), reflecting their willingness to engage in voluntary environmental conservation activities without expecting tangible rewards or recognition. This aligns with the Ability-Motivation-Opportunity (AMO) theory, which emphasizes the role of organizational practices in fostering employee engagement and pro-social behaviors (Appelbaum, Bailey, et al., 2000). However, the lower extent of pro-environmental behavior suggests that while foundational GHRM practices are well-established, there is room for enhancing proactive environmental initiatives among employees.

Age-related analyses indicated that older employees are more engaged in certain GHRM practices, such as green training and development, green human capital, and green structural capital, compared to their younger counterparts. This suggests that experience and tenure may play a role in the assimilation and execution of sustainability practices within the organization. Nevertheless, the absence of significant differences across sexes and lengths of stay underscores the effectiveness of the hotel's inclusive and equitable GHRM policies.

The significant positive correlation between GHRM and OCBE underscores the interdependent relationship between structured HRM initiatives and voluntary environmental behaviors. This indicates that robust GHRM practices not only provide the necessary resources and training but also cultivate an organizational culture that encourages employees to engage in environmentally responsible behaviors willingly (Hameed et al., 2020; Muisyo et al., 2022).

General Statements

The study elucidates the pivotal role of Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) in fostering a culture of sustainability within the hospitality industry. The high implementation levels of GHRM practices within the Filipino hotel brand demonstrate a proactive approach to environmental conservation, reflecting the organization's commitment to sustainable development. Employees' high levels of Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment (OCBE) further signify a workforce that is not only aware of but also actively participates in environmental stewardship. This synergy between GHRM practices and OCBE contributes to the hotel's enhanced environmental performance and operational efficiency.

Moreover, the qualitative insights reveal that the hotel's management effectively promotes environmental values through supportive and empathetic leadership, fostering a harmonious and motivated workforce. The emphasis on employee benefits, such as comprehensive medical coverage and continuous training opportunities, enhances employee satisfaction and loyalty, which are crucial for sustaining long-term environmental initiatives. The organizational culture, characterized by teamwork and empathy, plays a critical role in encouraging employees to go above and beyond their formal duties to support environmental sustainability.

The hotel's integrated approach to GHRM and OCBE not only bolsters its environmental performance but also enhances its reputation as a responsible and sustainable establishment. This positions the hotel favorably in the competitive hospitality market, attracting environmentally conscious guests and fostering a positive organizational image.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are proposed to further enhance the implementation of GHRM practices and OCBE within the Filipino hotel brand:

Enhance Pro-Environmental Behavior Initiatives. Given the lower extent of pro-environmental behavior, it is recommended that the hotel management develop targeted programs to encourage proactive environmental actions among employees. This can include structured incentive programs, recognition systems, and rewards for outstanding environmental contributions. Implementing a formal rubric as part of the annual performance appraisal process, aligned with key performance indicators related to GHRM and OCBE dimensions, can objectively identify and acknowledge employees' contributions to sustainability goals.

Strengthen Training and Development Programs. To bridge the gap in pro-environmental behaviors, the hotel should invest in comprehensive training programs that not only educate employees about environmental conservation but also empower them to take initiative in sustainability projects. Continuous professional development opportunities focused on environmental management and sustainable practices can further enhance green human capital.

Formalize Environmental Policies and Practices. While the qualitative data indicates effective informal practices, formalizing these policies in written documents such as employee handbooks can ensure consistency and clarity. Clear guidelines and procedures for environmental conservation efforts will help standardize practices across all departments and employee groups.

Promote Inclusive Leadership and Teamwork. The existing culture of empathy and teamwork is a significant asset. Management should continue to foster this environment by encouraging open communication, collaborative problem-solving, and collective participation in environmental initiatives. Leadership training programs that emphasize the importance of sustainability and ethical management practices can further strengthen this culture.

Implement Organizational Citizenship Behavior Enhancement Programs. To sustain and amplify OCBE, the hotel should consider developing OCB Enhancement Programs that specifically target environmental citizenship. These programs can include volunteer opportunities, community engagement projects, and partnerships with local environmental organizations, thereby integrating OCBE into the organizational ethos.

Focus on Employee Benefits and Well-being. Maintaining and expanding comprehensive employee benefits, such as medical coverage and career development opportunities, will continue to enhance employee satisfaction and loyalty. Recognizing the role of well-being in fostering a motivated and committed workforce is essential for sustaining GHRM and OCBE practices.

Expand Research and Continuous Improvement. Future research should explore the long-term impacts of GHRM and OCBE practices on organizational sustainability and financial performance. Additionally, conducting periodic assessments and feedback mechanisms can help identify areas for improvement and adapt strategies to evolving environmental challenges.

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